

**A FIXED POINT THEOREM BY USING PICARD ITERATIONS FOR GENERALIZED
 WEAK CONTRACTION OF INTEGRAL- TYPE IN G- METRIC SPACE**

¹Preeti Bhardwaj, ²Manoj Kumar

^{1,2}Department of Mathematics

^{1,2}Baba Mastnath University, Asthal Bohar, Rohtak, Haryana, India

E-mail: 1bpreetibmu9@gmail.com, 2manojantil18@gmail.com

KEYWORDS

ABSTRACT

Fixed points, weak contraction, Picard iteration

In this paper, we shall establish a fixed point theorem in G- metric space by using Picard iterations for generalized weak contraction of integral-type following the concepts of A. A. Branciari and B. E. Rhoades.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mustafa and Sims [9] introduced the notion of generalized metric space as follows:

Definition 1.1. Let X be a non empty set, and $G: X^3 \rightarrow R^+$ be a function satisfying:

- (G₁) $G(x, y, z) = 0$ if $x = y = z$;
- (G₂) $0 < G(x, y, z)$, for all $x, y \in X$, with $x \neq y$;
- (G₃) $G(x, x, y) \leq G(x, y, z), \forall x, y, z \in X$, with $z \neq y$;
- (G₄) $G(x, y, z) = G(x, z, y) = G(y, z, x) = \dots$;
- (G₅) $G(x, y, z) \leq G(x, a, a) + G(a, y, z), \forall x, y, z, a \in X$.

The function G is called a G -metric on X , and the pair (X, G) is called a G -metric space.

Definition 1.2. [9] Let (X, G) be a G -metric on X . A sequence $\{x_n\}$ is said to be

- i. G - convergent if for every $\varepsilon > 0$, there exist $x \in X$ and $m \in N$ such that for all $p, q \geq m, G(x, x_q, x_p) < \varepsilon$;
- ii. G -Cauchy if for every $\varepsilon > 0$, there exist $m \in N$ such that for all $p, q, r \geq m, G(x_p, x_q, x_r) < \varepsilon$, that is, $G(x_p, x_q, x_r) \rightarrow 0$ as $p, q, r \rightarrow \infty$.

If every G -Cauchy sequence in (X, G) is G -convergent, then space (X, G) is said to be G -complete .

Lemma 1.3. [9] Let (X, G) be a G -metric on X . The following statements are equivalent:

- i. $\{x_n\}$ is G -convergent to x ;

- ii. $G(x_q, x_q, x) \rightarrow 0$ as $q \rightarrow \infty$;
- iii. $G(x_q, x, x) \rightarrow 0$ as $q \rightarrow \infty$;
- iv. $G(x_q, x_p, x) \rightarrow 0$ as $p, q \rightarrow \infty$.

Lemma 1.3. [9] Let (X, G) be a G -metric on X . The following statements are equivalent:

- i. the sequence $\{x_n\}$ is G -Cauchy;
- ii. for every $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $G(x_q, x_p, x_p) < \varepsilon$ for $p, q \geq m$.

Definition 1.2. [8] For a G -metric space (X, G) a mapping $f : X \rightarrow X$ is called a contraction mapping on X if for any real number λ with $\lambda \in [0, 1)$, the following inequality holds:

$$G(fx, fy, fz) \leq \lambda G(x, y, z)$$

$$\int_0^{G(fx, fy, fz)} \varphi(t) dt \leq \lambda \int_0^{G(x, y, z)} \varphi(t) dt \text{ for all } f, g \in \mathfrak{S}.$$

$\varphi : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is a Lebesgue integral mapping, which is summable, such that for each $\varepsilon > 0$, $\int_0^\varepsilon \varphi(t) dt > 0$ and non- negative.

Definition 1.3. In 2012, Shatanawi and Postolache introduced the notion of G – weak contraction of type A in the following way:

Let (X, G) be a G – metric space. A mapping $f : X \rightarrow X$ is called a G – contraction of type A if and only if there exist two constants $a \in (0, 1)$ and $L \geq 0$ such that,

$$G(fx, fy, fz) \leq aM(x, y, y) + LN(x, y, y) \text{ for all } x, y \in X.$$

On getting motivation from this definition, we are introducing a new notion of (Y, E) generalized weak contraction of integral type in the following way:

Definition 1.4. Let (X, G) be a G – metric space. A mapping $f : X \rightarrow X$ is said to be a (Y, E) – generalized weak contraction of integral type if and only if there exist constants $\alpha \geq 0, E \geq 0$ and $\gamma \in [0, 1)$, such that for all $x, y \in X$,

$$\int_0^{G(fx, fy, fz)} \varphi(t) dt \leq \gamma \int_0^{G(x, y, z)} \varphi(t) dt + E \left(\int_0^{G(x, fx, fx)} \varphi(t) dt \right)^r \left(\int_0^{G(y, fx, fx)} \varphi(t) dt \right)^{[1-\alpha G(y, fx, fx)]}$$

(1)

where, $r \geq 0, 1 - \alpha G(y, fx, fx) > 0$

Remark 1.5. The contractive condition (1) does not require any additional condition for the uniqueness of the fixed point off.

2. Main Results

Theorem 2.1.

Let (X, G) be a complete G – metric space and $f : X \rightarrow X$ a (Y, E) – generalized weak contraction of integral type. Let $\varphi : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be a Lebesgue- integrable mapping which is summable, non-negative and such that for each $\varepsilon > 0$, $\int_0^\varepsilon \varphi(t)dt > 0$. Then, f has a unique fixed point $t \in X$, such that for each $x \in X$, taking limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have

$$f^n(x) = t.$$

Proof: Let $x_0 \in X$ and let defined by $x_n = fx_{n-1} = f^n x_0$, $n=1, 2, 3, \dots$ be the Picard iteration associated to f .

From (1), we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{G(x_n, x_{n+1}, x_{n+1})} \varphi(t)dt &= \int_0^{G(fx_{n-1}, fx_n, fx_n)} \varphi(t)dt \leq \gamma \int_0^{G(fx_{n-1}, fx_n, fx_n)} \varphi(t)dt + \\ E \left(\int_0^{G(x_{n-1}, fx_{n-1}, fx_{n-1})} \varphi(t)dt \right)^r &\left(\int_0^{G(x_n, fx_{n-1}, fx_{n-1})} \varphi(t)dt \right)^{[1-\alpha G(x_{n-1}, fx_{n-1}, fx_{n-1})]} = \\ \gamma \int_0^{G(x_{n-1}, x_n, x_n)} \varphi(t)dt &\leq \gamma^2 \int_0^{G(x_{n-2}, x_{n-1}, x_{n-1})} \varphi(t)dt \leq \dots \leq \gamma^n \int_0^{G(x_0, x_1, x_1)} \varphi(t)dt. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Taking the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{G(x_n, x_{n+1}, x_{n+1})} \varphi(t)dt &= 0 \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} G(x_n, x_{n+1}, x_{n+1}) &= 0 \quad (3) \\ G(x_{m(p)}, x_{n(p)}, x_{n(p)}) &\geq \varepsilon, \quad G(x_{m(p)}, x_{n(p)-1}, x_{n(p)-1}) < \varepsilon \quad (3.1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_0^{G(x_{m(p)}, x_{n(p)}, x_{n(p)})} \varphi(t)dt \\ &= \left\{ \int_0^{G(fx_{m(p)-1}, fx_{n(p)-1}, fx_{n(p)-1})} \varphi(t)dt \right. \\ &+ E \left(\int_0^{G(x_{m(p)-1}, fx_{m(p)-1}, fx_{m(p)-1})} \varphi(t)dt \right)^r \left(\int_0^{G(x_{n(p)-1}, fx_{n(p)-1}, fx_{n(p)-1})} \varphi(t)dt \right)^{[1-\alpha G(x_{m(p)-1}, fx_{m(p)-1}, fx_{m(p)-1})]} \left. \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Using (3)

$$[1 - \alpha G(x_{m(p)-1}, fx_{m(p)}, fx_{m(p)})] \rightarrow 1 \text{ as } p \rightarrow \infty, \quad (5)$$

$$\left(\int_0^{G(x_{m(p)-1}, fx_{m(p)-1}, fx_{m(p)-1})} \varphi(t)dt \right)^r \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } p \rightarrow \infty. \quad (6)$$

From (3) and (3.1) and triangle inequality, we get

$$\begin{aligned} G(x_{m(p)-1}, x_{n(p)-1}, x_{n(p)-1}) &\leq G(x_{m(p)-1}, x_{m(p)}, x_{m(p)}) + G(x_{m(p)}, x_{n(p)-1}, x_{n(p)-1}) \\ &< G(x_{m(p)-1}, x_{m(p)}, x_{m(p)}) + \varepsilon \text{ as } p \rightarrow \infty. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Using (3.1), (5), (6) and (7) in (4)

$$\int_0^\varepsilon \varphi(t)dt \leq \int_0^{G(x_m(p), x_n(p), x_n(p))} \varphi(t)dt \leq \gamma \int_0^\varepsilon \varphi(t)dt . \quad (8)$$

From which we obtain

$(1 - \gamma) \int_0^\varepsilon \varphi(t)dt \leq 0$, leading to $(1 - \gamma) > 0$. But $\int_0^\varepsilon \varphi(t)dt \leq 0$ and this is a contradiction by the condition on φ . Therefore, we must have that $\int_0^\varepsilon \varphi(t)dt = 0$, that is, $\varepsilon = 0$ from here, we conclude that $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy Sequence in X and (X, G) being a complete G –metric space sequence $\{x_n\}$ converges to an element, say, $t \in X$, i.e.,

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = t$. Also from (1), we have that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{G(x_{n+1}, ft, ft)} \varphi(t)dt = \int_0^{G(fx_n, ft, ft)} \varphi(t)dt \leq \gamma \int_0^{G(x_n, t, t)} \varphi(t)dt + \\ E & \left(\int_0^{G(x_n, fx_n, fx_n)} \varphi(t)dt \right)^r \left(\int_0^{G(t, fx_n, fx_n)} \varphi(t)dt \right)^{[1-\alpha G(x_n, fx_n, fx_n)]} = \gamma \int_0^{G(x_n, t, t)} \varphi(t)dt + \\ & E \left(\int_0^{G(x_n, x_{n+1}, x_{n+1})} \varphi(t)dt \right)^r \left(\int_0^{G(t, x_{n+1}, x_{n+1})} \varphi(t)dt \right)^{[1-\alpha G(x_n, x_{n+1}, x_{n+1})]} \quad (9) \end{aligned}$$

By taking the limits in (3.1) as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then we get

$$\int_0^{G(ft, t, t)} \varphi(t)dt \leq 0 \quad (10)$$

and from (10), we obtain a contradiction again.

Therefore, by the condition on φ , we have $\int_0^{G(t, ft, ft)} \varphi(t)dt = 0$

so that $G(t, ft, ft) = 0$, or $t = ft$.

Uniqueness of fixed point:

Let, if possible, there exist two fixed points $t_1, t_2 \in X$ such that $t_1 \neq t_2$, so $G(t_1, t_2, t_2) > 0$.

From (1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{G(t_1, t_2, t_2)} \varphi(t)dt \\ & = \int_0^{G(ft_1, ft_2, ft_2)} \varphi(t)dt \\ & \leq \int_0^{G(t_1, t_2, t_2)} \varphi(t)dt + E \left(\int_0^{G(t_1, ft_1, ft_2)} \varphi(t)dt \right)^r \left(\int_0^{G(t_2, ft_1, ft_1)} \varphi(t)dt \right)^{[1-\alpha G(t_1, ft_1, ft_1)]} , \end{aligned}$$

implies that,

$(1 - \gamma) \int_0^{G(t_1, t_2, t_2)} \varphi(t)dt \leq 0$, which gives us that

$1 - \gamma > 0$. But $\int_0^{G(t_1, t_2, t_2)} \varphi(t)dt \leq 0$

Thus, we get $\int_0^{G(t_1, t_2, t_2)} \varphi(t) dt = 0$ (By definition of φ)

Therefore, $G(t_1, t_2, t_2) = 0$, i.e., $t_1 = t_2$.

Hence, f has a unique fixed point.

References:

1. AGARWAL, R. P., MECHAN, M. AND O'REGAN, D., *Fixed Point Theory and Applications*, Cambridge University Press, 2001.
2. BANACH, S., *Sur les operations dans les ensembles abstraits et leur applications aux equations integrales*, Fund. Math. 3(1992), 133-181.
3. BERINDE, M., AND BERINDE, V., *On a general class of multi-valued weakly Picard mappings*, Journal Math. Anal. Appl., 326(2007), 772-782.
4. BERINDE, V., *Approximating fixed points of weak contractions using Picard iteratio*, Nonlinear Analysis Forum 9,1 (2004), 43-53.
5. BERINDE, V., *Apriori and a posteriori error estimates for a class of ϕ -contractions*, Bulletins for Applied & Computing Math, 90, B (1999), 183-192.
6. BRANCLARI, A., *A fixed point theorem for mappings satisfying a general contractive condition of integral type*, Int. J. Math. Math. Sci., 29, 9 (2002), 531-536.
7. CHATTERJEA, S. K., *Fixed-point theorems. C. R. Acad. Bulgare Sci.*, 10 (1972), 727-730.
8. MUSTAFA, Z., *A new structure for generalized metric spaces with applications to fixed point theory*, Ph.D. Thesis, The University of Newcastle, Australia, 2005.
9. MUSTAFA, Z. AND SIMS, B., *A new approach to generalized metric spaces*, J. Nonlinear Convex Analysis, 7(2006), 289-297.
10. MUSTAFA, Z. AND OBIEDAT, H., *A Fixed Point Theorem of Reich in G-Metric Spaces*, CUBO A Mathematical Journal, 12, 1(2010), 83-93.
11. RHOADES, B. E., *A comparison of various definitions of contractive mappings*, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc., 226 (1977), 257-290.
12. RHOADES, B. E., *Two fixed point theorems for mappings satisfying a general contractive condition of integral type*, Int. J. Math. Math. Sci., 63(2003), 4007-4013.